

New records of anamorphic fungi from Bulgaria

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Abstract. The anamorphic genus *Phloeosporina* (*Ph. fraxini*) and *Septoria dearnessii* are reported for the first time from Bulgaria. Seven fungus-host combinations, new for Bulgaria, are also recorded.

Key words: anamorphic fungi, Bulgaria, *Phloeosporina*, phytopathogenic fungi

The present paper includes new data on the anamorphic fungi of Bulgaria. The genus *Phloeosporina* (*Ph. fraxini* (Harkn.) Arx), and *Septoria dearnessii* Ellis & Everh. are reported as new taxa for Bulgaria. Short descriptions and illustrations are provided for these species. Seven fungus-host combinations, new for Bulgaria, as well as new localities for six anamorphic fungi are also recorded.

The fungi were identified with the aid of works by Sutton (1977, 1980), Brandenburger (1985), Nag Raj (1985), Teterevnikova-Babayana (1987), Brawn (1998), etc. Voucher specimens for all findings are deposited in the Mycological Collection of the Institute of Botany, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (SOMF).

List of species

New records for Bulgaria

Phloeosporina Höhn., Mykol. Unters. 1: 338, 1923.

For generic description see Braun (1998).

Ph. fraxini (Harkn.) Arx, Verh. Kon. Ned. Akad. Westensch., Afd. Natuurk., Tweede Sect. 51(3): 88, 1957. (Fig. 1)

Leaf spots 0.4–0.6 cm, circular or irregular, single or confluent, yellowish, ochre to brown, indistinctly delineated or limited by the leaf venation. **Acervuli** amphigenous, mostly epiphyllous, scattered, in groups or arranged in series parallel to the veins, rounded or elliptic, subepidermal, later breaking the epidermis, 100–500 µm in diam. **Conidia** cylindrical-fusiform, nearly straight to falcate, subtruncate at basal end, ta-

pered gradually towards the pointed apex, some rostrate, with one septum in the centre, sometimes guttulate, pale greenish, (17.5–) 19–29 × 2.5–4 µm.

On leaves of *Fraxinus excelsior* L. Sofia region: Bankya, 3 Sep 1985, E. Sameva (ES) (SOMF 22 196).

Septoria dearnessii Ellis & Everh., J. Mycol. 5: 151, 1889.

(Fig. 2)

Leaf spots 0.1–0.4 cm, rounded or irregular, pale brown to brown, limited by the leaf venation. **Pycnidia** amphigenous, scattered, globose or depressed globose, immersed, yellow-brown to brown, 35–75 µm in diam, with rounded or elliptic ostioles, 22–30 µm in diam, surrounded by dark brown cells. **Conidia** filiform, straight to slightly or moderately curved or scarcely flexuous, the base obtuse, gently tapered towards the narrowly obtuse apex, aseptate, sometimes 1–2-septate, hyaline, 15–36 × 1–1.5 (–2) µm.

On leaves of *Angelica sylvestris* L. Forebalkan: Lovech, 1889, leg. I. Urumov, fungus comm. & det. ES (SOMF 25 531).

Note. Several species of *Septoria* have been recorded on plants of *Angelica* s. lat. *Septoria angelicae* Höhn. and *S. xanthogali* Mekht. are similar to the present species. *S. angelicae* Golovin, renamed as *S. kravtzevii* Melnik, differs with thick-cylindrical, aseptate conidia, 37–63 × 4.6–5.7 µm.

Species with new hosts in Bulgaria

Ascochyta aquilegiae (Rabenh.) Höhn., Ann. Mycol. 3: 406, 1905.

Figs 1-2. Conidia of: 1 – *Phloeosporina fraxini*; 2 – *Septoria dearnessii*. Scale bar = 10 μ m

On leaves of *Aquilegia* sp. (hort.). Mt Sredna Gora: Mt Lozenska Planina, above the lake of Pancharevsko Ezero, 17 Jun 1998, ES (SOMF 25 532).

A. doronici Allesch., Hedwigia 36: 162, 1897.

On leaves of *Cichorium intybus* L. Vitosha region: Mt Vitosha, above Zheleznitsa, 6 Jul 2001, ES (SOMF 25 533).

Cercospora zebrina Pass., Hedwigia 16: 124, 1877.

On leaves of *Trifolium striatum* L. Vitosha region: Mt Vitosha, above Zheleznitsa, 6 Jul 2001, ES (SOMF 25 534).

Pestalozziella subsessilis Sacc. & Ellis, Michelia 2: 575, 1882.

On leaves of *Geranium robertianum* L. Balkan Range: near Zavodna river, 29 Jul 1971, S. Vanev (as *Pestalozziella geranii-pusilli* C. Massal.) (SOMF 16 472).

Phyllosticta stachydis Brunaud, Misc. Mycol. 2: 35, 1891.

On leaves of *Stachys germanica* L. Vitosha region: Mt Vitosha, above Zheleznitsa, 6 Jul 2001, ES (SOMF 25 535).

Ramularia lysimachiae Thüm., Fungi Austr. Exs., Cent. 12, no. 1177, 1874.

On leaves of *Lysimachia nummularia* L. Vitosha region: Mt Vitosha, above Zheleznitsa, 6 Jul 2001, ES (SOMF 25 536).

Septoria tormentillae Roberge ex Desm., Ann. Sci. Nat. Bot., ser. 3(8): 82, 1847.

On leaves of *Potentilla argentea* L. Vitosha region: Mt Vitosha, above Zheleznitsa, 6 Jul 2001, ES (SOMF 25 537).

New localities

Colletotrichum trichellum (Fr.: Fr.) Duke

On leaves of *Hedera helix* L. Valley of River Strouma: Petrich, 29 Oct 1982, ES (SOMF 22 162).

Monostichella salicis (Westend.) Arx

On leaves of *Salix alba* L. Sofia region: Sofia, 27 Oct 1985, ES (SOMF 22 163).

Septoria clinopodii Allesch.

On leaves of *Clinopodium vulgare* L. Vitosha region: Mt Vitosha, above Zheleznitsa, 6 Jul 2001, ES (SOMF 25 538).

S. crepidis Vesterg.

On leaves of *Crepis foetida* L. Black Sea Coast: Tsarevo, 24 Jun 1921, leg. B. Ahtarov, fungus comm. & det. ES (SOMF 25 539).

S. erigerontis Peck

On leaves of *Erigeron annuus* (L.) Pers. Thracian Lowland: Karlovo, 4 Jul 1998, ES (SOMF 22 164).

S. tanacetii Niessl

On leaves of *Tanacetum vulgare* L. Vitosha region: Mt Plana Mt., near Planashtitsa river, 8 Jul 1999, ES (SOMF 22 378).

Species of revised specimens published from Bulgaria

Microdochium panattonianum (Berl.) B. Sutton, Galea & T.V. Price, Trans. Brit. Mycol. Soc. 86: 620, 1986.

On leaves of *Lactuca sativa* L., as *Marssonina panattoniana* Berl. (Atanasov *et al.* 1932) and *Marssonina panattoniana* (Berl.) Magnus (Bakalova 1999).

Pestalotiopsis maculans (Corda) Nag Raj, Mycotaxon 22: 47, 1985.

On leaves of *Rosa* sp. (cult.), as *Pestalozzia guepinii* Desm. (Savov 1923) and *Pestalotiopsis guepinii* (Desm.) Steyaert (Bakalova 1999).

P. neglecta (Thüm.) Steyaert, Trans. Brit. Mycol. Soc. **36**: 83, 1953.

On leaves of *Euonymus japonica* Thunb. (cult.), as *Pestalotia neglecta* Thüm. (Vanev & Taseva 1990).

Truncatella laurocerasi (Westend.) Steyaert, Bull. Jard. Bot. État **19**: 298, 1949.

On leaves of *Malus sylvestris* Mill. (as *Pyrus malus* L.), as *Pestalozzia malorum* Elenk. & Ohl (Hristov 1934) and *Pestalotiopsis laurocerasi* (Westend.) Y. X. Chen (Bakalova 1999).

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